

**SAMARKAND HISTORY AND ARCHITECTURE OF HISTORIC
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Annotation. This article provides information on the socio-economic aspects of the reconstruction of existing historical city blocks, the most important role of the microdistrict system in the development of the socio-economic life of the city and the construction of microdistricts in the future, the cultural development of cities.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о социально-экономических аспектах реконструкции существующих исторических городских кварталов, важнейшей роли системы микрорайонов в развитии социально-экономической жизни города и строительстве микрорайонов в будущем, культурном развитии городов.

Key words: *Mahalla, history, social, socio-economic, significance, development, cultural, spiritual, community, city.*

Ключевые слова: *Махалля, история, социальное, социально-экономическое, значение, развитие, культурное, духовное, сообщество, город.*

Introduction. One of the main priorities in the development of science in the republic is associated with the repair, restoration and use of architectural monuments of Uzbekistan for modern purposes. One of the main priorities in the development of science in the republic is associated with the repair, restoration and use of architectural monuments of Uzbekistan for modern purposes. In the development of tourism, not only public buildings, but also residential buildings and historical

quarters, which are preserved as monuments, are included in the Yunusco list and are of interest to foreign tourists.

Material and Methods. One of the features that distinguish the historical cities of Uzbekistan from other ancient cities is that most of the monuments in these cities were built in the form of an architectural ensemble - a group of buildings - a set of urban planning laws created at that time. The organization and decoration of the interiors of the traditional folk houses of Samarkand were studied, and in the early 19th and early 20th centuries, a new modern direction was outlined in a combination of eastern and western methods of architectural decoration.[1]

Formation and organization of modern tourist centers, expansion of their composition, development of their structure, increase in architectural expressiveness, change of historical centers and development of adjacent territories. At the same time, the architects are faced with the task of carefully preserving all historically valuable elements from the historically established structure to the modern building, creating a harmonious unity of the old and new buildings. The complexity of solving this problem lies in the fact that in the center of historical cities the height of buildings usually does not exceed 1-2 floors, although modern construction is mainly focused on high-rise buildings, it is necessary to create a harmonious unity of buildings

In the context of the incompleteness of the socio-economic aspects of the restoration of existing historical city blocks, they are constantly changing and the problem of bringing the structure of the city in line with modern requirements for the growth of the city in quantitative terms, functional zoning of the territory, the technical condition of capital buildings, the level of engineering equipment and improvement, urban transport, providing new social functions that meet the modern aesthetic requirements of society.

The most important condition for the development of a historic city is the satisfaction of the socio-economic needs of modern society. This is why the city exists, and this is its essence. When planning and building settlements, one should take into account the scientific and historical or architectural and artistic significance

and cultural monuments that are under state protection. Around groups of monuments and cultural monuments, a buffer zone and a development regulation zone should be provided in agreement with organizations for the protection of cultural monuments.[2]

The construction of new buildings and structures within the boundaries of the buffer zone is not allowed without the permission of organizations for the protection of cultural monuments. The emergence of a new category of "construction regulation zone", i.e., the expansion of the boundaries and functions of the protection of the architectural heritage, determines the connection of the leading structure with the environment, currently only in the immediate vicinity of the monument.

In the historical cities of Uzbekistan, mahallas develop as follows: Samarkand was divided into 7 districts and had 30 guzars. In Bukhara, the city is divided into 12 districts, each of which has 5-7 mahallas. In Tashkent the city is divided into 5 districts and more than 30 mahallas, in Khiva the city is divided into 7 districts and more than 67 mosques are divided into tribes. The cities of the Ferghana Valley are also divided into dachas and mahallas. historical and typological development of regional centers can be divided into five stages: the ancient period - BC. VI-IV centuries; Muslim period - VII-XIII centuries; Timurid period - XIV-XV centuries; the period of the Uzbek khanates; the period of Russian colonization - the twentieth century (the period from 1917 to the present).[4]

The classification of mahallas, developed in four stages, was studied by M. Abramov, A. Pisarchik and many other researchers before the revolution. The above information is based on sources left by these scientists. Thus, the main conditions for the formation of regional centers were ideological, socio-economic and economic factors. They contributed to the creation of district centers, their appearance, the new look of quarters, played a formative role in the city and had a great influence on the renewal of its compositional and environmental composition, influencing the growth of the city in territorial terms. [3]

Narrow streets among traditional settlements prevail on each street of the historical part of Samarkand, and mosques and teahouses stand out for their

compositional solution in this environment. Although these houses have a complex appearance, public buildings (mosques, teahouses, district centers) are included in the planning structure of these streets. The quarters were located in a proportional plane between settlements, at a distance of 450-500 meters between them. Passers-by enjoyed the compositional atmosphere of the labyrinth of narrow streets and made their way to the main street from the distant minaret of the mosque.

Conclusion. Each structure has its own potential, which depends on the nature of the city, the compositional environment, the densely populated residential areas in the city, and district centers play a key role in the planning structure of the city. They reflect the historical street in the structure of the microdistrict, once again proving that Samarkand is a historical city. The development of projects for the reconstruction of the historical part of the city and its environs is carried out on the basis of historical-architectural and historical-urban planning research. These studies should be carried out not only before the draft master plans of cities, the design and construction of centers, but also at all stages of development.

LITERATURE

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